

miR Name	transcript name	leftmost position of predicted target site	folding energy (in -Kcal/mol)	heteroduplex	p value
hsa_let_7a_5p	OR134577.1	14	-18.90	TGCT--CCAACCTGCTGCTGCA : : : : TTGATATGTTGGATGATGGAGT	2.31E-1
hsa_miR_15b_5p	OR134577.1	12	-14.70	AGTGCTCCA--ACCTGCTGCTG : : ACATTTGGTACTACACGACGAT	2.31E-1
hsa_miR_15a_5p	OR134577.1	14	-13.00	TGC--TCCA--ACCTGCTGCTG : : GTGTTTGGTAATACACGACGAT	2.31E-1

Table. 1. RNA22 v2 results obtained for three tumor suppressing miRs (TS-miR) on the 20 bp fragment [CTCCAACCTGCTGCTGCAGT], corresponding to the bases 5905–5924 of Spike protein ORF in Pfizer bivalent expression vector BNT162b2 (GenBank: OR134577.1) found to be integrated within chromosome 19 (chr19:55,482,637–55,482,674, GRCh38) as published by Catanzaro *et al.* 2025. Areas marked RED correspond the sequence of the integrated fragment, containing the „seed” region for TS-miRs analysed in this study (see: miR name). Heteroduplexes between other miRs and Pfizer bivalent expression vector BNT162b2 are available in [Supplementary Data - S1](#).